

Soft Values in Port-city Relationships: Case of Reidi Road and Port of Tallinn

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ABSTRACT: Ports and cities have historically been strongly linked and developed in close association with each other. This study focuses on analysing the case of Tallinn Reidi Road. The methodology is based on tangible soft assets of ports based on framework Soft Values of Ports. The aim of this study is to clarify how cooperation between Port of Tallinn AS and the City of Tallinn, through the Reidi Road project, has influenced the visibility, perception, and integration of tangible soft values in port-city relationships. The case study demonstrates how different stakeholders assess and experience the multidimensional role of a port in society. Results indicate that the Port of Tallinn and the City of Tallinn acknowledge and value the significance of soft values. In addition, this study provides practical recommendations and suggestions that can help city and port officials, policy makers and urban planners to better understand and integrate soft values in future development projects. In particular, soft value initiatives should be incorporated by port authorities in cooperation with local authorities.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ports and cities have historically been strongly linked and developed in close association with each other [6]. The relationship between ports and cities is strongly interconnected and supportive, where increased port activity led to more city activity and increased city activity led to increased port activity [7]. But on the other hand, port activity may create problems in relationships between the port and the city. Noise, congestion of city traffic and restricted access to waterfronts are not welcome by citizens. If ports want to succeed in improving their public image, they should clearly understand the various societal harms for which they are held responsible.

Based on literature, the interaction between ports and cities has mainly been considered from the perspective of economic benefits and infrastructure development. The systematic inclusion of soft values in

port development projects is a less well-known area of research, which allows to broaden the understanding of the multi-faceted nature of port and urban development.

This study focuses on the case of Reidi Road construction in Tallinn from the point-of-view of port-city relationships. Reidi Road was a building project of a new road to city harbour in the old town of Tallinn [20]. The road was mainly intended for lorries travelling from Estonia to Finland and Sweden in passenger-car ferries. The outline of the project was approved in April 2015 and the sources of funding for the road construction were the European Union, Port of Tallinn and City of Tallinn [3, 19]. The road was opened at the end of November 2019. Reidi Road development project in Tallinn is an attempt to integrate urban space and the port area. The aim of this study is to clarify the visibility and impact of soft assets, often less recognized method in port

development, yet essential for creating high-quality and people-friendly urban spaces.

Port of Tallinn is one of the largest and busiest passenger ports in the Baltic Sea region, significantly impacting both the urban and economic landscape of the City of Tallinn. In 2024, the port handled more than 8,5 million passengers, reflecting its essential role as a maritime gateway between Estonia and other major cities in the Baltic Sea area, especially Helsinki and Stockholm. More than 4500 ferry calls annually highlight the port's intensive maritime traffic, underscoring its strategic and economic importance. Furthermore, the port's passenger flows directly contribute to the urban economy by stimulating local businesses, tourism, and the hospitality sector, reinforcing the port-city integration. The intense ferry traffic and high passenger volumes also underline the necessity for effective urban and maritime infrastructure projects—such as the Reidi Road—to harmonize port activities with urban life, ensuring smooth logistics, better accessibility, and improved quality of urban spaces.

Figure 1. Map of Reidi Road (Estonian Land and Spatial Development Board, 2025)

The case study of this paper provides practical recommendations and suggestions that can help city and port officials, policy makers and urban planners to better understand and integrate soft values in future development projects. In particular, soft value initiatives should be incorporated by port authorities in cooperation with local authorities.

In general, development projects such as Reidi Road in Tallinn are designed to improve the city's infrastructure and public space, but their impact on the port and urban space and the local community is not always clear.

The research questions of this study are:

- How has the Reidi Road project influenced cooperation and perceptions between the City of Tallinn and Port of Tallinn AS from the perspective of different stakeholders?
- What is the impact of the Reidi Road project on the local community, businesses and the general well-being, and how is it perceived by different stakeholders?
- How have soft values been integrated into the Reidi Road project, and how are they perceived by different stakeholders?

This paper consists of four sections. The first section is a review of the literature on port-city cooperation. The second section describes the methodology, research strategy, stakeholders and their selection. The third section presents the main findings of the

research and offers recommendations for further action. In the final section, the conclusions are drawn and future research discussed.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Most of the world's important and large cities have developed in coastal areas or in areas with well-developed water connections. Transport facilities led to the initial development of many large metropolitan areas [17]. Ports enabled small towns to grow into large cities, stimulating the urban development associated with the boom in trade [15]. Ports created cities and large ports created metropolitans [17]. Historically, every coastal city had a port, and the port fed the city [7].

Spatial changes at the interface between port and city have always been preceded by changes in port development. Looking at the development of British ports, Bird's (1963) Anyport model describes port infrastructure development over time and space [1]. Notteboom (2010), expanding Bird's model with global economic and supply chain perspectives, distinguishes four phases of port evolution: location, expansion, specialization, and regionalization [18].

The concept of the port-city interface concept was first introduced by Hayuth (1982). He pointed out that technological advances and the modernisation of port activities have increased public interest in coastal areas [9]. This change accelerated the process whereby ports moved away from urban cores, downstream, causing a weakening of the relationship between cities and ports and reducing the traditional uses of urban fringe. Hayuth stressed the importance of port-urban interface areas from both a spatial and functional perspective, describing them as geographical boundaries between port areas and urban areas, or the temporal transition between port and urban areas. Already before Hayuth, the port has been described through the social transformations of the port-urban relationship [21]. Hoyle's model of port-city development adopts a chronological approach to port-city relations and, in the final stage, highlights the renewed cooperation that we see today between port and city as waterfront zones are revitalised [12].

Port areas are some of the most urbanised and complex places on the planet, with the highest levels of entrepreneurship and diversity, while providing the best conditions for cities and industries to thrive and create economic and social prosperity [4]. Daamen argues that today's major seaport-urban mix is evolving differently from that of some 20 years ago, and a new interpretation is needed to support sustainable development. This calls for an interdisciplinary approach to the contemporary port-urban interface, encompassing not only its spatial but also its economic, socio-cultural and environmental characteristics.

The concept of a port city has been defined in a very vague way, with varying definitions and content. The function and economic structure of a port city depends on several elements, ranging from the physical conditions of the location to global trade trends [2]. For this reason, different types of port cities are distinguished. According to Vigarié, cities with port

functions (e.g. Le Havre) are characteristically differentiated from regional industrial cities, which are more land transport oriented (e.g. Rouen, Manchester, Szczecin), and from large cities, which provide services and are often located on the coast (e.g. New York, London, Hamburg, Copenhagen).

Ducruet has drawn up a matrix of the relationship between ports and cities, which depicts nine different types of port-city relationship and is based on the concepts of centrality and intermediary, developed earlier by Hayuth [5]. The matrix considers that centrality is the functional dimension of the city, and intermediacy is the functional dimension of the maritime domain.

Three concepts have been defined in the literature - city and port, city port and port city - to describe the interaction between a city and a port. The concept of port-city is not always clearly defined, as the functions of port and city are rarely fully balanced. These concepts emphasise the interdependence of port and city and the importance of their joint development in an economic and cultural context.

Table 1. Definitions of city and port, urban port and port city (Rauk, 2024)

Concept	Explanation
City and port	The term refers to the relationship and interaction between two different but closely related entities: the city and the port. These relationships are dynamic and influence each other's economic, social and spatial development. The port can influence the economic prosperity and strategic positioning of the city, while the city provides the port with infrastructure, labour and markets.
City port	A harbour located in close proximity to, or closely integrated with, a city, providing commercial and leisure facilities. Urban ports are often centres of economic activity in a city, linking maritime and urban life and promoting tourism, culture and business.
Seaport city	A term referring to a city whose economic, social and cultural life is closely linked to port and maritime activity. These are cities where port activity is central to the identity, history and development of the city, serving as important commercial, transport and tourism hubs, linking sea and land transport and facilitating international trade and cultural exchange.

It is important to understand that the relationship between port and city changes over time, going through several stages from economic dependence to diversification, where the city can develop independently of port activities. Murphey, for example, argues that a seaport city is destined to become a general city through successive stages of economic diversification. The first stage is defined by the city's economic dependence on maritime and port functions, the second stage marks the addition of complementary activities (e.g. industry) and the third corresponds to the development of a service economy, which allows the city to free itself from port dependency [16].

Port city territories have been built and administrated to facilitate flows of goods, people, and ideas between a maritime foreland and what is often a transnational hinterland. These flows depend on

carefully curated tangible and intangible borders to guide the formation of spaces and social patterns that enable specific kinds of movement [11].

Jansen has similar ideas as Van Hooydonk [10]. Jansen states that we need to embrace a holistic, inclusive approach to port city development, based on ecosystems values, embedded in various layers of capital: natural, cultural, social, human, industrial and creative [13]. Port-city symbiosis requires an ecosystem approach, emphasizing spatial, social, economic, and cultural interconnections between port territories, urban space, and coastal ecosystems. Such an integrated approach ensures that ports can serve as catalysts for sustainable urban development, promoting inclusivity and resilience [14].

Van Hooydonk has classified the soft values that are important for the functioning and development of ports, but not always at the forefront of the port's activities. According to Van Hooydonk, port areas need to be visible, accessible and attractive to maintain public interest in and support for port development. His concept aims to propose ideas for a more efficient use of the port's diverse assets and functions and to generate interest and inspiration for local port and city authorities on how to regain public support for their activities. It will also increase the interest of the public, and in particular ordinary people, in seaports and the attractiveness of port cities as some of the most influential places in the world.

Van Hooydonk's theory of Soft Values Management for Seaports develops relationships between port and port-cities based on non-economic values. These include historical, sociological, psychological, artistic, cultural and even moral and religious sub-functions, which together form the soft function of ports. Soft values help to understand the wider impact of ports on society and culture, beyond their economic and operational functions. The soft values of ports are divided into two main categories: spiritual and material soft values.

Spiritual soft values of seaports are:

- the seaport as an object of worship, myth and legend;
- the seaport as a place of refuge;
- the seaport as a gateway between historical eras;
- the seaport as an international conduit for free trade and merchandise;
- the seaport as a breeding ground for human intelligence;
- the seaport as a specific cosmopolitan community;
- the seaport as an artistic theme;
- the seaport as a source of civic pride.

Tangible soft of seaports are:

- the seaport as a sensory stimulant;
- the seaport as a collection of immovable heritage;
- the seaport as a unique man-made landscape;
- the seaport as an experimental field for urban planners and architects;
- the seaport as a tourist attraction and recreation resort.

This study focuses on analysing the case of Reidi Road in Tallinn is based on tangible soft values of the port. Reidi Road project is a good example where tangible soft assets - such as promenade design, traffic management innovations and public space aesthetics -

are of key focus. This case study is practically valuable in helping to better understand and shape port-city cooperation and the quality of public space. The analysis provides practical recommendations on how to integrate port and urban space.

3 RESEARCH METHODS

The focus of this study was the impact of the cooperation between Port of Tallinn AS and the City of Tallinn in the context of the Reidi Road development project focusing on tangible assets of soft values of ports. The study employs a qualitative case study approach focused on the Reidi Road development project. The primary method used to collect data was semi-structured stakeholder interviews in order to get a more comprehensive understanding of the views, experiences and opinions of different stakeholders and to capture in-depth insights regarding perceptions and experiences related to the cooperation between Port of Tallinn AS and the City of Tallinn in the context of the Reidi Road development project. Stakeholder interviews were tailored specifically to each stakeholder group's unique perspective and expertise.

The study focuses on the impact of the cooperation between AS Tallinna Sadam and the City of Tallinn in the context of the Reidi Road development project, focusing mainly on the soft values of the ports.

A total of purposefully selected 16 people took part in the survey: 2 representatives of Port of Tallinn; 3 representatives of the City of Tallinn; 4 architects/city planners and 4 representatives of citizens; 3 representatives of tourism sector. Selection was based on their direct involvement, professional expertise, and experience with the project, ensuring diversity in perspectives. Port representatives are employees of Port of Tallinn responsible for the port's operations and strategic development, who influence the relationship between the city and the port through their operational and strategic decisions.

City representatives include specialists from the Tallinn City Government and experts involved in urban planning and development, playing a key role in city governance and the formulation and implementation of urban development policies. Architects and urban planners were selected as one stakeholder group because their expertise significantly influences how port areas are integrated within the urban structure. The involvement of local residents was extremely important, as they directly benefit from or are affected by the Reidi Road development project. All residents participating in the survey were selected based on their direct experience with or proximity to the Reidi Road area. Representatives of the tourism sector, especially cruise tourism, were involved due to the importance of tourism in connecting city planning and port development. Their views help shape future strategies to promote sustainable city-port tourism.

Each stakeholder questionnaire contained 6 open-ended questions adapted to the specificity of the stakeholder group, one similar question with multiple-choice answers and one similar question on agreement with statements.

Based on Van Hooydonk's framework, stakeholders' assessments of the port's tangible soft values were analysed, based on five aspects: 1. port as a sensory stimulus; 2. the port as a real estate asset; 3. the port as a unique human landscape; 4. the port as an experimental testing ground for urban planners and architects; 5. the port as a tourist and recreational destination.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Tangible assets

The following chapter analyses the assessments of various stakeholder groups regarding the tangible soft values of the port. Results of the interviews are as follows (see also Figure 2).

Figure 2. Tangible soft values, average estimates of stakeholders (Rauk, 2024).

4.1.1 Seaport as a sensory stimulant (sensory sensations: the sound of seagulls, the roar of ships' engines, the special smell of the harbour, dining places complemented by a lively nightlife, visual sensations)

City representatives give a very high evaluation (5.00) to the visual and sensory appeal of the port, seeing it as an attractive element for drawing visitors and enhancing the city's reputation. The image of the port as a vibrant and diverse place can be highly valuable for the city's representatives, helping to create an appealing and positive impression. Architects and port representatives also give a relatively high evaluation (4.00). Architects, who work with designing spaces and environments, may appreciate the port's aesthetic and functional versatility, finding it a source of inspiration and professional interest. For port representatives, the sensory stimuli of the port are everyday experiences. Their relatively high evaluation may stem from the positive and dynamic work environment. Representatives of tourism sector acknowledge port's potential to attract tourists, but their relatively low evaluation (3.33) may reflect concerns about certain aspects of the port, such as noise and smells, which may not always be appealing to visitors. Citizens, in their daily lives, may be more sensitive to and affected by the less attractive aspects of the port environment, such as noise, odours, and crowds, which could explain their low evaluation (3.25). The low evaluations from citizens and tourism sector representatives may also indicate that they do not consider sensory stimuli to be a priority.

Overall, each group interprets and evaluates the port differently, based on their own experiences, professional interests and expectations. As a recommendation, the positive sensory experiences of the port area could be enhanced by:

- investing in the visual appeal of the port;
- developing innovative lighting solutions;

- supporting and developing dining options in the port area that offer local flavours;
- organizing cultural and entertainment events in the port.

4.1.2 *Seaport as a collection of immoveable heritage (port buildings; monuments of port-related architecture; statues, pillars and other sculptures)*

The maximum rating from city representatives (5.00) likely reflects an understanding of the port's heritage as an inseparable part of the city's identity and history. Architects, whose work is often closely linked to aesthetics and historical value, give a fairly high rating to the port's real estate heritage (4.50). They appreciate the architectural legacy of the port as an important part of the city's architectural history. The relatively high rating from tourism industry representatives (4.33) indicates recognition of the role of the port's heritage in making the city more attractive to visitors. However, while they see its potential, a better presentation may be needed. Port representatives value the port's real estate heritage highly (4.00). This may indicate awareness of its historical and cultural significance, yet with a practical approach to port development, they also see room for improvement. Citizens give the lowest rating (3.25), which may indicate that the presence of port heritage is not perceived as a key factor in their everyday lives.

In conclusion, the port's heritage is generally highly valued. However, to further enhance its significance, there is a need for better awareness and presentation.

Some recommendations for strengthening the value of the port's real estate heritage:

- develop tourism programs that offer guided tours and activities in the historical areas of the port;
- encourage local artists and craftspeople to create and sell works that reflect the history and culture of the port;
- integrate elements of the historic heritage into new developments, creating a bridge between the past and the future.

4.1.3 *Seaport as a unique man-made landscape (every port is unique due to its distinctive natural conditions and the human decisions shaping it, influenced by technological advancements in shipping)*

City representatives give the highest rating (5.00), indicating that they see the port as an essential part of the cityscape and identity. They recognize the unique value of the port in aesthetic, social, and economic terms. The high rating from port representatives (4.50) reflects their appreciation of the port's uniqueness and significance.

Architects also give a strong rating (4.25), which may reflect their professional interest in the port's landscape and functional aspects. They acknowledge the complexity of port planning while also seeing opportunities for improvement.

Citizens and tourism industry representatives give a slightly lower rating (4.00) compared to other stakeholder groups. For citizens, the port's value may be less visible or not directly relevant in their daily lives. Tourism industry representatives may recognize the port's uniqueness as a selling point but might also feel that its full potential has not yet been realized.

In conclusion, different stakeholder groups have a generally positive attitude toward this perspective. Some recommendations for the port and the city:

- make greater use of the port's unique natural features to strengthen its identity and distinctiveness;
- launch initiatives that support biodiversity and the preservation of natural habitats in the port area (e.g. creating of nature parks, ecological corridors for safe animal movement between different parts of the port);
- develop infrastructure that highlights the port's uniqueness, such as improving promenades and viewing platforms;
- organise port days or open house events that allow visitors to experience port activities.

4.1.4 *Seaport as an experimental field for urban planners and architects (reorganizing port areas and transforming the port district into a vibrant, multifunctional space can revitalize urban areas and significantly help ports regain public support for their activities.)*

The city representatives have given the highest rating to this statement (4.67), highlighting their strong belief in the positive impact of port area redevelopment on urban development. They see the port as a valuable resource that can revitalize urban space and contribute to city planning goals. The high rating from port representatives (4.50) reflects their openness to new uses and multifunctionality in port areas, recognizing the importance of innovation and development.

Similarly, architects (4.50) view the port as a potential hub for innovative solutions and appreciate the opportunity to apply new design ideas to create diverse spaces. Tourism industry representatives acknowledge the potential of port areas for tourism and leisure, but their rating (4.33) suggests a degree of caution, as redevelopment could impact existing tourist attractions. Citizens have given the most reserved rating (4.00), indicating that while they recognize the significance of the port, it may not be their primary concern. Overall, the ratings reflect a broad appreciation of the port as a platform for urban planning and architectural experimentation.

Some recommendations for the city and the port to shape port areas into an innovative and dynamic environment:

- organise international competitions to attract new ideas for port area redevelopment;
- involve the community and local businesses at an early stage to ensure broad support and a clear understanding of needs;
- collaborate with universities and other research institutions to establish ports as centres of innovation and scientific research;
- design port areas to be easily adaptable to future needs, rapidly evolving technologies, and societal trends;
- ensure strong connectivity between port areas and other parts of the city by offering diverse transport options (pedestrian paths, bicycle lanes, public transport, etc.);
- develop port areas to support a range of economic activities, including craftsmanship, commerce, leisure, and entertainment opportunities.

4.1.5 *Seaport as a tourist attraction and recreation resort (the port is a destination for tourism and leisure activities, including sightseeing, fishing and visit to maritime museums and marinas, as well as a hub for excursions, entertainment and educational initiatives)*

The maximum rating given by port representatives (5.00) indicates a strong belief that the port is, and should remain, a key tourist attraction, with high-quality activities and services that appeal to visitors. City representatives rate the port at (4.33), recognizing its role in tourism and leisure within the city. They see the development of the port as a tourism destination as an important factor in enhancing the city's overall attractiveness and economic well-being. Architects give a rating of (4.00) to the port's potential as a tourist attraction, which likely reflects their appreciation of its aesthetic and functional possibilities while also acknowledging room for further development. Citizens provide a lower rating (3.00), suggesting that they may not perceive the port as an attractive leisure destination for their own use.

The lowest rating comes from tourism industry representatives (2.67), which is significant and may indicate a need to further develop the port's recreational and tourism offerings to better meet their expectations. This could suggest perceived shortcomings in tourism infrastructure, services, or marketing efforts.

The ratings reflect varying perceptions of the port as a tourist attraction and leisure destination. The high ratings suggest significant potential and support, while the lower ratings indicate a need to address certain shortcomings. In particular, tourism industry representatives should be more actively involved in the port's development to enhance the overall tourism appeal of the area and ensure that the experiences offered by the port meet visitors' expectations.

Some recommendations for the city and the port to enhance the port area as a tourist attraction and leisure hub:

- create a vibrant meeting place in the port area by offering entertainment, dining, and cultural experiences (e.g. organizing street music performances, temporary markets, festivals);
- make historic port buildings accessible to tourists by transforming them into galleries or museums;
- engage local schools and communities in educational programmes focused on maritime history and marine biology to increase interest in the port and raise awareness of local maritime heritage;
- develop active leisure packages offering various activities such as sailing, kayaking, diving and fishing tours;
- launch a strong marketing campaign that highlights the port's unique features and attractions;
- establish partnerships with tourism businesses to create tailored visitor experiences that meet the expectations and needs of specific target groups.

Overall, the ratings reflect how each stakeholder group perceives the value of the port from their own perspective and interests. While there is clear support for the port's development in a various roles, the differences in the ratings indicate areas that could be

improved to fully realize the port's potential for both local residents and tourists.

4.2 *Future development of port-city relationships*

Representatives from various stakeholder groups, a total of 16 individuals, provided ratings on five different statements regarding ways in which the city of Tallinn can further strengthen its role as a bridge between the city and the sea. Respondents could express their agreement with each statement by marking an 'X' in the table.

Figure 3. Responses on the role of the City of Tallinn in strengthening the relationship between the city and the sea (Rauk, 2024)

Transport and accessibility received the strongest support from respondents. All 16 respondents considered this statement important, as it plays a key role urban planning and has a direct impact on people's daily lives. A well-functioning transport system and good accessibility directly influence the city's vitality, economic development, and people's ability to move and interact. The daily need for fast and efficient transport holds practical value, which is why it received strong support from various stakeholder groups. Port representatives emphasized that smart traffic management and a shuttle bus service around the Old Town would further improve the transport connection between the city and the port. City representatives highlighted the expansion of the tram network, which will make public transport between the port and the city more convenient and faster.

The development of port districts and public spaces received broad support from all stakeholder groups, with 14 respondents considering it important. This type of development is not just about aesthetic; it also enhances functionality, making these areas more attractive for living, working and leisure. Port districts and public spaces are central to the city's visual identity and daily life, offering opportunities for community gatherings and social interaction. However, some respondents did not consider this aspect as a priority, as they believe there are even more critical areas for development that require attention. Additionally, concerns were raised about gentrification, as port district redevelopment could lead to rising living costs and the displacement of local residents. Furthermore, large-scale development projects along the coastline or in environmentally

sensitive areas may have negative environmental impacts.

Collaboration and community engagement were considered important by 13 respondents. The success of cities increasingly depends on community participation and involvement in decision-making processes. Active community engagement fosters stronger connections between residents and local authorities, leading to better solutions that address the needs of all stakeholders. It is also essential for ensuring sustainable urban development. Moreover, involving the community reduces resistance to new initiatives, as people feel included in the process. Respondents emphasized that early involvement is key to securing broad support and understanding community needs. Additionally, they highlighted the importance of gathering feedback on completed developments and changes to assess their impact on residents' daily lives and whether they have met expectations. This was seen as particularly crucial when making traffic management adjustments or planning new development projects.

The organisation of cultural events and educational programmes received slightly less support (11 respondents agreeing with the statement) because, although they have a positive impact on the quality of urban life and the image of the city, their direct impact on daily life and the city's infrastructure may be less visible compared to, for example, transport. The impact of cultural events and educational programmes are often long-term and less tangible, making their immediate value harder to recognize. Respondents highlighted the Tallinn Maritime Days, considered Estonia's largest maritime and family festival. The event is organized by the City of Tallinn in collaboration with AS Tallinna Sadam, the Estonian Maritime Museum, Noblessner, and various other partners. In 2024, instead of the traditional maritime festival, The Tall Ships Races Tallinn 2024 will take place, offering an even grander maritime celebration. Additionally, the Seaplane Harbour (Lennusadam) and Noblessner regularly host diverse music and theatre events, attracting large numbers of visitors to the waterfront.

The promotion of sustainable tourism received the least votes (10 respondents). This may reflect a more niche interest, primarily relevant to specific stakeholders (such as tourism businesses) but not necessarily a priority for others. For example, citizens who did not consider this important may be more focused on improving the daily life of the local community rather than enhancing visitor experiences. It may also have remained a misunderstood concept, requiring specific knowledge or further clarification. Sustainable tourism aims to actively reduce the negative impact of travel on both people and the planet. Some respondents also pointed out limited resources should be prioritized for more urgent needs, such as urban infrastructure or social services. Suggestions were made to increase greenery in public recreational areas and create small parks to improve the overall quality of urban leisure spaces.

These statements highlight priority areas to addressing the dynamics between the city and the sea. They provide an overview of different stakeholder interests, emphasize the need for sustainable

approaches in culture, tourism, transport, and accessibility, and underscore the importance of collaboration and community engagement in urban planning and strengthening local identity. These insights offer valuable information for developing action plans and policies that are based on the specific assessments and expectations of various stakeholder groups.

As conclusion the following general recommendations can be made to improve the situation:

- organise open forums and workshops to involve the community in urban planning and port development projects;
- improve feedback collection mechanisms and ensure that citizens input is considered in actual urban planning initiatives;
- develop and renovate public spaces to make them more attractive and comfortable for recreation, living, and working;
- organise cultural events and educational programmes that elevate the city's cultural profile and provide educational entertainment;
- implement environmentally sustainable solutions to reduce the negative impacts of development projects and improve the overall environmental quality;
- continue efforts to improve accessibility and mobility for pedestrians, cyclists and public transport users, creating a more people-friendly and safer urban space;
- encourage and promote eco-friendly transport options, such as cycling and walking, to reduce traffic congestion and improve air quality.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The Reidi Road development project is an important example of how infrastructure development can improve the relationship between the port and the city, enhancing the quality of life for local communities, businesses, and urban life as a whole. The development project emphasises the importance of soft values in the integration of the port and the city, serving as a cultural and social space that shapes perceptions, relationships and collaboration.

The aim of this study was to analyse the success story of the Reid Road development project as a port and urban space integration project, focusing on its impact on the local living environment, community well-being, and cultural and historical heritage from the perspective of managing soft values in ports.

In summary, the development project has significantly influenced the relationship and cooperation between the Port of Tallinn and the City of Tallinn, mostly in a positive way, although some challenges have emerged.

The analysis of the case study carried out shows how the multidimensional role of the port in society is assessed and experienced by different stakeholders. Citizens' assessments directly reflect the local community's perspective, illustrating how port activities and developments influence daily life and overall quality of living. Architects, often involved in shaping port areas, provide insights into the

significance of aesthetic and structural aspects in port development. Port representatives' perspectives help identify the impact of the port's soft values on business strategies of port operators and how port activities affect the wider social and cultural landscape. Tourism industry representatives offer valuable input on how the port could be better marketed and developed as an attractive destination, thereby increasing visitor numbers and economic revenue. City officials and public sector views play a crucial role in securing political support and funding for port-related projects.

Responses from city and port representatives reveal several key differences and similarities. Both stakeholder groups acknowledge that the Reidi Road development project has improved cooperation and relationships between the city and the port. They confirm that the development project has improved the quality of life and increased the attractiveness of the public spaces.

Port representatives highlight their willingness to cooperate with the city but also point out collaboration challenges. They highlight the project's positive impact on port operations, particularly in traffic flow management and improved access. However, they are more critical of the increased traffic noise and congestion, which negatively affect quality of life. Port representatives focus on existing and future collaboration projects and infrastructure improvements that support sustainable tourism.

City representatives focus on the project's broader impact on urban space and the community. They emphasize improvements in the living environment, the expansion of leisure opportunities, and positive changes in urban planning and strategies resulting from the project. Additionally, they acknowledge the project's contribution to cultural heritage preservation and awareness-raising, as well as its role in promoting environmental and sustainability goals.

The architects' evaluations reflect broad appreciation for the positive aspects of the Reidi Road development project, including the attractiveness of the pedestrian areas and the waterfront promenade. Some concerns remain regarding environmental solutions and community engagement practices within the project.

Citizens' assessments focus more on changes in daily life and living environment. Although the project has not had a significant impact on their quality of life, they see room for improvement, especially in terms of community involvement and expanding leisure opportunities.

Tourism industry representatives recognize the opportunities created by the Reidi Road development project, but they also see a need for better cooperation and involvement in port and city planning, especially in the early stages of projects.

As a result of the analysis, it can be said that Port of Tallinn and the City of Tallinn are aware of the existence of soft values and recognize their importance. Based on the above-mentioned theory, they have not systematically mapped, analysed, or applied these values, but they emphasise their necessity and integrate them into their daily projects.

As a summary of the analysis, it can be concluded that all stakeholder groups acknowledge the sensory impact of the port and its importance as a cultural and social space; recognize the importance of the port's historical and architectural heritage, which adds value to the area; agree on the port's uniqueness and its role in the urban landscape; appreciate the port's potential as a part of innovative urban planning; and acknowledge the port as a key destination that attracts both locals and tourists.

Overall, it appears that while different stakeholders have different expectations and concerns regarding the project, they all share a common recognition of its contribution to improving urban space and community quality of life.

The limitations of the case study are primarily due to the reserved attitude of interviewees. They expressed preconceived opinions about the Reidi Road development project, which may have hindered their full openness and willingness to provide detailed explanations. More extensive questionnaires and a larger number of interviews could have helped uncover new perspectives and enriched the study.

A recommendation for future research involves applying the theory of soft values in ports through comparative studies. Given the qualitative nature and limited scope of the study, the findings presented here should be interpreted as illustrative and exploratory rather than comprehensive or generalizable. Future research employing mixed-methods approaches, including quantitative surveys and multi-criteria indicator analyses, would further enhance understanding and validate the insights gathered in this study. The aim is to analyse the practices of ports around the world to understand how cultural, social and environmental contexts influence the integration of soft values in ports. This approach will help gather insights into best practices and innovative methods for enhancing the integration between ports and cities.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations can be made for the future: continue and expand the involvement of local communities, businesses and stakeholders in port and urban development projects, emphasising transparency and inclusiveness; increase awareness of the soft values of ports through educational initiatives, information boards, and guided tours to enhance public recognition and appreciation.

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